

RESIST Digital Shepherd: An open-source onboarding and information platform

This document serves as a reference point to the open-source software repository of the RESIST Digital Shepherd.

RESIST Digital Shepherd is an interactive onboarding and information platform built with React + TypeScript + Vite. This open-source UI guides users through climate adaptation data preparation, regional analysis, and integration with digital twin technologies for the RESIST EU project.

Repository: <https://github.com/SINTEF/os-digital-shepherd>

Online demo: <https://resist.hcilab.no/demo/shepherd/> (credentials: admin/demo)

RESIST Digital Shepherd was developed by: Ophelia Prillard (SINTEF), Maria Emine Nylund (SINTEF), and Costas Boletsis (SINTEF) with the valuable contributions of: Scott Young (AugmentCity), Danny Vandenbroucke (KU Leuven), Vida Farhadibansouleh (KU Leuven), and Jiaxin Li (SINTEF).

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